

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 2.48

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.846481

DOI URL: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.846481>

Cite this paper as : Puja Kumari & Manoj Kumar & Jitender Singh (2017). "BATTERY STATES CONTROLLING BY PV SYSTEM", International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research, Volume 4,(Issue 4, Jun-2017), pp 41–50. ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online) , ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print), **DOI URL: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.846481>**

BATTERY STATES CONTROLLING BY PV SYSTEM

Puja Kumari

M.Tech. (Pursuing) GITAM,
Kablana, Jhajhar, Hariyana

Manoj Kumar

Assistant Professor Radha
Govind Engineering College,
Meerut

Jitender Singh

Assistant Professor GITAM,
Kablana, Jhajhar, Hariyana

Abstract:

The paper presents the modeling of a standalone PV system in Matlab/Simulink environment. The PV model is developed using basic circuit equations of the photovoltaic (PV) solar cells including the effects of solar irradiation and temperature changes. A DC/DC Boost converter is used to increase the array voltage to that of battery and connected DC load. The buck converter is controlled to extract the maximum power output of PV panel. The equations of the model are presented in details. First the mathematical modeling of a solar cell is done, then how a solar module, array and panel is obtained using that cell is shown clearly. Different characteristics of cell, module, and array have been obtained for different parameters. Secondly a standalone model of PV system in modeled and battery state controlling is carried out. Solar PV panel is a nonlinear power source that needs accurate identification of optimal operating point. It is desired to operate Solar Photo Voltaic (SPV) panel at its maximum power output for economic reasons. This paper is useful to model, simulate and study the effect of changing ambient conditions of a standalone PV system and also useful for Battery state controlling.

Index Terms— Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT), SPV Array , Battery. MATLAB Simulation.

INTRODUCTION

With the increasing problems due to pollution, it has become the need of time to switch over to the renewable energy sources. Development and utilization of renewable energy and green energy is necessary for pollution control and for sustainable development . The solar energy is the ideal green energy and a photovoltaic (PV) system is the most simple and reliable way to produce electricity from the conversion of solar energy . In Photovoltaic (PV) generation photo diodes convert solar energy into electrical energy and maximum power point is tracked by MPPT.

PV energy is widely used renewable energy sources because of its a variety of advantages as easy installation, pollution free, low maintenance cost etc. However, the disadvantage of PV system is intermittent, depending upon weather conditions. Thus any another resource is used to get stable and reliable power from PV system for drawing the load i.e. a storage bank or we can say battery bank. Hence steady and dynamic behaviors of PV system are improved. Because of its developed technology, low cost and high efficiency battery system are generally used in dispersed generation system. Battery is integrated to PV system in hybrid and distributed system for more

reliability and stability. This integrated system is composed of PV system, MPPT, Boost Converter, load, power electronic converters, controllers etc.

MODEL OF THE SYSTEM COMPONENTS

PV generation system consists of photovoltaic array with MPPT for maximum power point tracking, battery system, boost converter, rectifier, controller and other devices. Schematic diagram of basic system is shown in fig-1. That how PV system is integrated with battery to draw the load [2].

Fig. 1. Model of the System Component

When PV system is generating excessive power after drawing the load, will be supplied to feed the battery until it is in its SOC (State of Charge). Opposite to it, when the PV system is generating lesser power, the battery will draw the load partly to assist the PV system to draw the load until it is in its SOD (State of Discharge).

To determine the overall system performance, individual PV systems need to be modeled first and then their overall system performance can be evaluated to draw the load smoothly.

SOLAR SYSTEM

Solar System is one of the most popular non-conventional energy system. PV panels convert solar energy into electrical energy with non-linear internal characteristics. The voltage power characteristics depends upon variation of isolation and temperature. With high initial installation cost, it is always necessary to operate PV at its maximum power point. For this proposed dc-dc interfacing PV-wind and battery system is required [3]. Commonly used single diode 100 KW PV array is used in this work. The power flow from PV panel is controlled via boost converter and MPPT is used to find out the peak power of the PV panel.

PV array consists of N_{par} strings of modules connected in parallel, each string consisting of N_{ser} modules connected in series.

Number of series connected modules per string (N_{ser}) = 5;

Number of parallel strings (N_{par}) = 66

Fig. 2. PV cell equivalent circuit (Lorenzo, 1994)

PV cell can be represented by the simple equivalent circuit shown in Fig.2. The output current is the function of solar radiation, temperature and coefficients that are particular to the cell technology.

PV CELL CHARACTERISTICS

A PV cell can be represented by a current source connected in parallel with a diode, since it generates current when it is illuminated and acts as a diode when it is not. The equivalent circuit model also includes a shunt and series internal resistance. R_s is the intrinsic series resistance whose value is very small. R_p is the equivalent shunt resistance which has a very high value.

The basic equation from the theory of semiconductors that mathematically describes the I-V characteristic of the ideal Photovoltaic cell is:

$$I_{PV} = I_{ph} - I_D \tag{1}$$

Where;

I_{ph} = Current generated by the incident light (it is directly proportional to the Sun irradiation)

I_D = Shockley Diode Equation

$$I_D = I_{Sat} [e^{\frac{V_D}{V_T}} - 1] \tag{2}$$

Where;

I_{Sat} = Diode Saturation Current or Leakage Current of the Diode.

V_D = Diode Voltage (Volts)

$V_T = \text{Temperature - Voltage}$

$$V_D = V_{PV} + I_{PV}R_S \quad (3)$$

$$V_T = \frac{KT}{qQ_d N_{Cell} N_{Ser}} \quad (4)$$

Where;

$V_{PV} = \text{PV cell Voltage}$

$I_{PV} = \text{PV cell Current}$

$R_s = \text{Intrinsic Series Resistance}$

$T = \text{Cell Temperature (K)}$

$k = \text{Boltzmann Constant } (1.3806503 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J/K})$

$q = \text{Electron Charge } (1.60217646 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C})$

$Q_d = \text{Diode Quality Factor}$

$N_{Cell} = \text{No. of Series Connected Cells per module}$

$N_{ser} = \text{No. of Series Connected modules per string}$

MAXIMUM POWER POINT TRACKING (MPPT)

Maximum Power Point Tracking, frequently referred to as

MPPT, is an electronic system that operates the Photovoltaic (PV) modules in a manner that allows the modules to produce all the power they are capable of. MPPT is not a mechanical tracking system that "physically moves" the modules to make them point more directly at the sun. MPPT is a fully electronic system that varies the electrical operating point of the modules so that the modules are able to deliver maximum available power. Additional power harvested from the modules is then made available as increased battery charge current. MPPT can be used in conjunction with a mechanical tracking system, but the two systems are completely different.

The proposed MPPT controller tracks the peak power of the PV module based on the incremental conductance method.

Maximum Power Point is obtained when:

$$\frac{dP}{dV} = 0$$

(5)

Where;

$$P = V \times I$$

(6)

$$\frac{d(V \times I)}{dV} = 0$$

$$I + V \frac{dI}{dV} = 0$$

$$\frac{dI}{dV} = -\left(\frac{I}{V}\right) \quad (7)$$

Where;

dI, dV = fundamental components of I and V ripples measured with a sliding time window T_MPPT

I, V = mean values of V and I measured with a sliding time window T_MPPT

The integral regular minimizes the error $\left(\frac{dI}{dV} + \frac{I}{V}\right)$

Regulator Output = Duty Cycle Correction

The MPPT gives the pulsating signal which is fed to IGBT in Boost Converter for Step up of PV Panel Output.

BOOST CONVERTER

The boost converter is a high efficiency step-up DC/DC switching converter. The converter uses a transistor switch, in proposed system IGBT is used, to pulse width modulate the voltage into an inductor. Rectangular pulses of voltage into an inductor result in a triangular current waveform.

BATTERY

Battery systems are used because of its features as wide operating temperature range, low self-discharge, long service life and maintenance free. Installation cost of battery is low but lifetime cost is high compared to PV system because of its limited service time.

Battery life time is reduced if there is low PV energy availability for longer period i.e. improper charging and discharging. So battery charging requires control of achieving

SOC (State of Charge) and longer battery life.

Hence proper controller for battery charging is required. The

main function of battery charging in PV-wind System is to fully charge without permitting overcharging while preventing reverse current flow and deep discharge under low conditions.

A simple equivalent circuit model structure for Ni-MH

(Nickel-Metal-Hybrid) battery is used to facilitate the battery model part of the system model.

The proposed discharge model is similar to the Shepherd model but can represent accurately the voltage dynamics when the current varies and takes into account the open circuit voltage (OCV) as a function of SOC. A term concerning the polarization voltages added to better represent the OCV behaviour and the term concerning the polarization resistance is slightly modified.

The battery voltage obtained is given by:

$$V_{\text{batt}} = E_0 - k \frac{Q}{Q-it} it - Ri + Ae^{(-Bat)} - k \frac{Q}{Q-it} \cdot i^*$$

(8)

Where;

V_{batt} = Battery Voltage

E_0 = Battery Constant Voltage

K = Polarization Constant (V/Ah) or Polarization Resistance (Ω)

Q = Battery Capacity (Ah)

$It = \int it =$ Actual Battery Charge

A = exponential zone amplitude (V)

B = exponential zone time constant inverse (Ah)⁻¹

R = internal resistance

I = Battery current (A)

I^* = Filtered current

The particularity of this model is the use of a filtered current flowing through the polarization resistance. In fact, experimental results show a voltage slow dynamic behaviour for a current step response.

This filtered current solve also the algebraic loop problem

due to the simulation of electrical systems in Simulink. Finally, the OCV varies non-linearly with the SOC. This phenomenon is modelled by the polarization voltage term.

The exponential zone of above is valid for the Li-Ion battery.

For the other batteries (Lead-Acid, NiMH and NiCD), there is a hysteresis phenomenon between the charge and the discharge, no matter the SOC of the battery.

$$e^{(t)} = B \cdot |i(t)| \cdot (-e^{(t)} + A \cdot u(t)) \quad (9)$$

Where;

$e^{(t)}$ = exponential zone voltage (V)

$i(t)$ = battery current (A)

$u(t)$ = charge or discharge mode

the exponential voltage depends on the initial value and the charge ($u(t) = 1$) or discharge mode.

THE CHARGE MODEL

The charge behaviour, particularly the state of the charge (SOC) characteristic, is different and depends on the battery type. The Ni-MH batteries have a particular behaviour at SOC.

Indeed, after the battery has reached the full charge voltage, the voltage decreases slowly, depending on the current amplitude. This phenomenon is very important to model because a battery charger monitors the ΔV value to stop the charge. This behaviour is represented by modifying the charge polarization resistance. When the battery is fully charged ($i = 0$), the voltage starts to drop. The charger continues to overcharge the battery ($i < 0$) and the voltage decreases. This phenomenon can be represented by decreasing the polarization resistance when

$$\text{Pol. Resistance} = k \frac{Q}{|i| - 0.1 Q} \quad (10)$$

the battery is overcharged by using the absolute value of the charge ():

Similar to the discharge model, the exponential voltage for these batteries is given by:

$$e^{(t)} = B \cdot |i(t)| \cdot (-e^{(t)} + A \cdot u(t)) \quad (11)$$

Charge Model Overview:

$$E_{\text{batt}} = E_0 - k \frac{Q}{|it| - 0.1Q} i - k \frac{Q}{Q - it} . it + e^t \quad (12)$$

POWER ELECTRONIC CIRCUIT (UNIVERSAL BRIDGE)

Power electronic circuits are used in converting electrical

energy. To have a common source in the hybrid system that combined wind and PV model, power converter is needed to convert alternating current (AC) to direct current (DC) or vice versa. The converting is perform by solid-state semiconductor devices that operate with periodically switched on and off at a desired frequency. Therefore, power electronic converter also known as switching converter because the output is controlled by switches.

Here, power converter AC-DC Universal Bridge

Rectifier is used to complete the hybrid wind and PV model.

SIMULINK MODELLINGS

Fig.4. Controlling of SOD & SOC of Battery via PV

The waveform above obtained explains that the PV array sized at 18 string in series and 218 string at parallel generating a voltage of 850V peak and a constant supply of 500V at STC of the module. The state of charging (SOC) is set at 1 and state of discharging is 0.8 of 200V battery which is obtained successfully by proposed system.

CONCLUSION

The study presents a PV array to attain a nominal voltage with proper string sizing of the plant as 18 strings in series and 218 strings in parallel. The wind turbine is provided with the cut in speed of 3m/s and cut out speed at 30m/s getting a DC supply by connecting a universal bridge. The both system are synchronized parallel with battery of 200V 6.5AH as shown in model of system components with SOC and SOD parameters set at 1 and 0.8 thereby providing a good nominal voltage and Charging-Discharging states of the battery is successfully attained.

This system can be used to satisfy demand of the consumer by connecting the system to the grid or can be feasible as a standalone system at the remote location to light up India future with a renewable power.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sergio Daher, Jurgen Schmid and Fernando L.M Antunes, “Multilevel Inverter Topologies for Stand-Alone PV Systems” IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics.Vol.55, No.7, July 2008.
- [2] Eftichios Koutroulis, “Methodology for optimal sizing of standalone photovoltaic/wind-generator systems using genetic algorithms,” Solar Energy 80. ELSEVIER: 2006, pp. 10721088.
- [3] Chiang, S.J. Shieh, H.J. Chen, M.C. —Modeling and Control of PV Charger System with SEPIC Converterl. Industrial Electronics, IEEE Transactions, Vol.56, no.11, Nov 2009

- [4] Electronics, IEEE Transactions, Vol.56, no.11, Nov 2009J.M.A. Myrzik and M.Calais "Sting and Module Intigratrd Inverters for Single –Phase Grid-Connected Photovoltaic Systems – Review" IEEE Bologna Power Tech conference, June 2003.
- [5] "Modeling and Analysis of Single Phase Grid Connected Photovoltaic System" SWATI BHASME, DR. A.P. REVANKAR Research Scholar, Govt. Engineering College
- [6] exchange anisotropy," in Magnetism, vol. III, G. T. Rado and H. N. Femia, G. Petrone, G. Spagnuolo and M. Vitelli, " Optimizing sampling rate of P&O MPPT technique," in proc. IEEE PESC, pp. 1945-1949, 2004.
- [7] "Analysis and Implementation of Grid-Connected Solar PV with Harmonic Compensation" Jianwu Cao, Florida State University, 4 January 2011.
- [8] Photovoltaic Systems-An Overview" Center for renewable Energy systems Technology IEEE 1998.
- [9] "Fault Condition Analysis in a Grid Connected PV Energy System" Abbas Haijing, Zulkeflee khalidin, Electrical and Electronic Faculty, University Malaysia Pahang, 2011 International Conference on Circuits, System and Simulation IPCSIT vol.7 (2011)© (2011) IACSIT Press, Singapore.
- [10]"Power Quality in Grid Connected Renewable Energy System:Role of Custom Power Devices" by S.K.Khadem, M.Basu and M.F.Conlon Electrical Power Research Group,School of Electrical Engineering Systems, Dublin Institute of Technology, Kevin Street, Dublin 8, Ireland, 23-25 March 2011.